

over a period of 10 min. The stirring was continued for an additional 20 min. After usual work up, the methylene chloride solution was dried (CaCl_2). Evaporation of the solvent gave the corresponding mesylate (V, 4 g) which was used as such without further purification. Its IR spectrum showed the absence of any peak in the hydroxy region but had characteristic band at 1180 cm^{-1} .

12-(Tetrahydro-2'-pyranlyoxy)-2, 4-dodecadiene (VI): The above mesylate (V) in DMSO (5 ml) was added to NaBH_4 (0.8 g) in DMSO (20 ml) at 18° during one hr period and the colourless solution was stirred for an additional one hr. The mixture was slowly added to cold 3N HCl and the product was extracted with pet ether and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation gave the pyranyl ether (VI, 2.2 g) in 63% yield, b.p. $125^\circ\text{-}30^\circ/8 \text{ mm}$. ν_{max} 2940, 1625, 1450, 1380, 1325, 1290, 1265, 1205, 1165, 1135, 1080, 1035, 990, 908, 870, 815, 755 and 730 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 76.37; H, 11.58. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.64; H, 11.35 %).

Trans-8, trans-10-dodecadien-1-ol (I): A mixture of pyranyl ether (VI, 2.2 g), PTS (1.1 g) and methanol (20 ml) was shaken at 60° for 2 hr. The product was extracted with ether. The combined extract were washed with dil. NaHCO_3 solution and dried. The solvent was then evaporated and the residue on distillation gave alcohol (I, 1.2 g) in 80% yield, b.p. $105^\circ/6 \text{ mm}$. Tlc

showed single spot (Rf 0.265, Chloroform ethylacetate 4 : 1). ν_{max} 3385, 2940, 1625, 1450, 1435, 1375, 1350, 1320, 1260, 1205, 1128, 1080, 1055, 985, 918, 905, 870, 840 and 815 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 79.45; H, 12.45. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}$ requires C, 79.06; H, 12.16%).

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References

1. L. M. MCDONOUGH, D. A. GEORGE, B. A. BUTT, M. JACOBSON and G. R. JOHNSON., *J. Econ. Entomol.*; 1969, **62**, 62.
2. W. ROELOF's, A. COMEAU, A. HILL and G. MILLICEVIC., *Science*, 1971, **174**, 297.
3. C. DESCOINS and C. A. HENDRICK., *Tetrahedron Letters* 1972, 2999.
4. O. P. VIG, A. K. VIG, J. C. MANN and K. C. GUPTA., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).
5. W. S. WADSWORTH and W. D. EMMONS., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1733.
6. L. D. BERGELSON and M. M. SHEMYAKIN., *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 149.
7. E. I. SNYDER., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, **32**, 3531.
8. R. K. CROSSLAND and K. L. SERVIE., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 3195.
9. E. J. COREY, H. A. KIRST and J. A. KATZENELLENBOGEN., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 6317.